

THE INFLUENCE OF COMMUNICATION AND *LEADERSHIP* ON TEAM PERFORMANCE THROUGH MOTIVATION VARIABLES IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF PATIENT SAFETY CULTURE IN THE SERVICE UNIT OF IBNU SINA HOSPITAL MAKASSAR

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Abstract

In order to achieve optimal patient safety, it is important for health institutions, both medical and non-media staff, patients and families to work together to implement best practices and communicate well to ensure safe, effective and high-quality care. This research aims to determine the influence of communication and leadership on team performance through motivational variables in implementing patient safety culture in the service unit of Ibnu Sina Makassar Hospital. The research method used is a quantitative approach with a *cross-sectional approach* study and data collection using a questionnaire distributed to hospital employees in the emergency room, ICU, outpatient, IBS and HD. The sample for this research used a total sampling method of 78 people. The research results show that leadership has a significant influence on communication, motivation and performance. Communication has a significant influence on motivation and performance. Motivation has a significant influence on performance. There is an indirect influence between communication and performance through motivation. There is an indirect influence between leadership and performance through motivation. Good communication and effective leadership can influence performance indirectly through increasing the motivation of team members at RSU Ibnu Sina Makassar.

Keywords: Communication, Leadership, Motivation, Performance, and Hospital Employees.

INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, patient safety is regulated in several laws and regulations related to health services and patient protection. Several relevant laws that cover aspects of patient safety include Law Number 36 of 2009 concerning Health which provides a general framework for the implementation of the health system in Indonesia. Although it does not specifically address patient safety, this law states the importance of providing safe and quality health services .

Incidents that can occur in health care facilities, especially in hospitals, which can affect patients, staff, or anyone who is in the hospital include Potential Injury Conditions (KPC), Near Injury Events (KNC), Non-Injury Events (KTC), and Unexpected Events (KTD). This problem is not limited to patients. In one Danish study, involvement in patient safety incidents resulting in moderate harm, severe harm, or death was systematically associated with higher psychological burden for staff that could affect their performance (Elewa, 2019; Sarasanti et al., 2018) .

In order to achieve optimal patient safety, it is important for health institutions, both medical and non-media staff, patients and families to work together to implement best practices and communicate well to ensure safe, effective and high-quality care. Hospitals have a very important role in maintaining and improving patient safety.

Patient safety is a top priority in the hospital environment, and various efforts are made to prevent injury or unwanted risks during treatment (Hedyastuti et al., 2020) .

Table 1: Number of Patient Safety Incidents at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar 2020-2022

Incident Case	Year			Ministry of Health Standard No. 125 of 2008
	2020	2021	2022	
KTD	5	4	1	0
KNC	5	2	2	0
KTC	4	1	2	0
Sentinels	1	0	0	0

Source: Ibnu Sina Hospital Quality Committee Section, 2023

From the table above, it shows that there were 4 types of patient safety incidents that occurred at Ibnu Sina Hospital during 2020 to 2022. The number of adverse events in 2020 was 5 cases, then in 2021 there were 4 incidents and in 2022 there was 1 case, then KNC in 2020 there were 5 cases and in 2021-2022 there were 2 cases of KNC incidents each. There were 4 KTC incidents in 2020, 1 incident in 2021 and 1 incident in 2022, then 1 sentinel incident occurred in 2020. Meanwhile, based on Ministry of Health regulation no. 129 of 2008 concerning Minimum Hospital Service Standards has stipulated that there should be no number of KTD, KNC and KTC in hospitals (standard 0 cases). The large number of incidents at Ibnu Sina Hospital indicates that Ibnu Sina Hospital needs to carry out an evaluation so that in the future it can reduce, if necessary, eliminate patient safety incidents .

Based on the results of a quantitative survey of 12 dimensions of patient safety culture in hospitals. Ibnu Sina showed that there is a culture of patient safety in hospitals. Ibnu Sina's safety culture is categorized as "weak" with an average value of 44.34%. This occurs based on the results of calculating the total percentage value of the incident report frequency category at Ibnu Sina Hospital, only 41.30%, supervisors' expectations and activities to support safety are only 36. 80%, the response confirmed the occurrence of errors was only 26.92%, staffing or division of workload was only 26.93%, handoffs and shift changes were only 7.44% and team collaboration between units was only 43.11%. A patient safety culture is said to be strong if the average respondent has a positive response of 75% or more, it is said to be moderate if the average respondent has a positive response of 50% - 75%, it is said to be a weak culture if the average number of respondents has a positive response. positive < 50%. Positive responses are responses that answer agree and strongly agree to positive statements and disagree or strongly disagree to negative questions. A negative response is the opposite of a positive response

Another resource that is no less important to pay attention to in implementing a patient safety culture in hospitals is providing training to staff, both medical and non-medical. Hospitals must facilitate training activities for staff regarding patient safety practices, including use of medical devices, medication handling, infection control, and emergency treatment procedures. This training helps increase staff awareness and competence in maintaining safety (Saryadi, 2018) .

Research on the influence of communication and leadership on team performance through motivational variables in the implementation of patient safety culture has significant relevance in the context of health services.

Here are some reasons why it is important to research these variables:

1. **Patient Safety:** Implementing a patient safety culture is crucial in the healthcare environment to prevent medical errors, reduce the risk of complications, and improve overall patient care. Understanding the influence of communication and leadership on team performance through motivation can help improve the effectiveness of patient safety culture implementation.
2. **Communication Effectiveness:** Effective communication within a healthcare team is essential to prevent errors and promote good coordination. Examining how communication influences motivation and ultimately team performance can provide insights for developing better communication strategies in the context of safety culture.
3. **Leadership Role:** Strong and effective leadership can be a catalyst for increasing team motivation and performance. Understanding how leadership influences safety culture and motivation can help healthcare organizations identify the most appropriate leadership models to achieve patient safety goals.
4. **Motivation as a Performance Driver:** Motivation has a central role in determining the extent to which team members actively participate in safety culture efforts. This research can provide a deeper understanding of the motivational factors that contribute to team performance, so that organizations can design more effective motivation programs.
5. **Integrating Variables:** Integrating communication, leadership, motivation, and team performance variables in one study can provide a holistic view of the relationships between these variables. This can help in identifying key factors that influence the implementation of patient safety culture.

By examining these variables, we can gain a better understanding of the dynamics within healthcare teams and formulate more effective intervention strategies to improve patient safety culture.

Based on the data and problem formulation above regarding patient safety incidents at Ibnu Sina Hospital, and the research results that have been presented, researchers are interested in conducting research to analyze the influence of communication, motivation and leadership on team performance in implementing patient safety at Ibnu Sina Hospital, Makassar .

LITERATURE REVIEW

Patients Safety (Safety Patient)

Safety patient is something system Where House Sick making patient care safer. The system includes: *assessment* risks, identification and management of matters related to risks patients, incident reporting and analysis, ability to learn from incidents And follow he continued as well as implementation solution For minimize risk arises. It is hoped that this system can prevent this from happening injury caused as a result of carrying out an action or not do action Which should done (Huriati et al., 2022).

Team Performance

Team performance *is* the main determining factor And often used as indicator success something company. So that something group work can run effectively, every member

of the group should have their respective duties and roles. Work roles (*task roles*) is an effort made by each member of the group so that all activities can be coordinated well. Besides that, Through clear work roles, new ideas will be obtained and can be achieved solve problems well (Susilowati et al., 2020).

The success of achieving the strategy needs to be measured, because measurement is a key aspect of performance management on the basis that if it is not measured it will not be able to improve. Therefore, strategic targets that are the basis for measuring performance need to be determined in size, and strategic initiatives determined to realize these targets. Strategic targets and their measurements are then used to determine the awards that will be given to personnel, teams or organizational units (Susilowati et al., 2020) .

Communication

Communication is one of the things that is very necessary to get maximum work results from each employee's work. Communication is a process of transferring understanding in the form of ideas and information from one person to another. A similar definition was also put forward by Muhammad (2009) in (Mubarak et al, 2022) who stated that communication is the process of individuals sending stimuli, usually in verbal form, to change the behavior of other people.

Based on the various definitions that have been put forward, it can be concluded that communication is a process of exchanging information, thoughts or ideas carried out by two or more people to convey aims and objectives so that what is desired can be achieved.

In order to communicate effectively in various contexts and with various groups of people, it is important to understand and appreciate the differences in the various types of communication that exist. Communication consists of several types because humans interact in various contexts and situations that require different ways of communicating. Each type of communication has different characteristics, goals and contexts, giving rise to variations in the types of communication used (Elewa, 2019; Olausson et al., 2022)

Motivation

Motivation is a term that comes from the Latin word *movere* , which means *to move* . Motivation is an important determinant of individual performance. However, apart from motivation, there are other variables that also influence performance, such as the effort (work) exerted, the ability of the person concerned and previous (work) experience (Winardi, 2011).

Motivation is classified as a part of psychological factors which act as the main factor that encourages a person to act to achieve a goal, both personal and organizational goals that have been determined previously. Motivation is a characteristic of human psychology that contributes to a person's level of commitment. Motivation will encourage someone to do something. Someone who is motivated will do work or exercise power, especially in behavior (Efliani et al, 2015).

Motivation is a feeling or thought that can encourage someone, especially in behavior so that someone can fulfill their needs and desires. In fulfilling their needs, a person will behave in accordance with the impulses they have and what underlies their behavior, so it can be said that within a person there is strength. When employees

have high motivation, it will have an impact on increasing their performance (Devito, 2017).

Leadership

Leadership is a person's ability to influence, motivate and direct other people or groups in achieving predetermined goals. Leadership involves the process of leading, organizing, inspiring, and directing people using appropriate skills and strategies (Adair, 2009).

Effective leaders usually have several key characteristics, including self-confidence, good communication, the ability to inspire and motivate others, decision-making abilities, and the ability to work in a team. Apart from that, Leadership also involves the ability to identify and utilize individual strengths, provide constructive direction and feedback, and solve problems (Devito, 2017).

Leadership is a process in which leaders influence, inspire and motivate their followers to achieve high performance and develop their full potential (Bass & Riggio, 2006). Leadership is a person's ability to influence and guide others in achieving set goals (DuBrin, 2015).

Conceptual Framework

MATERIALS METHODS

Research Design

This research uses an analytical observational research approach, with a *cross-sectional approach* study or cross section, namely research variables are measured or collected at one time

Location and Research Plans

The research location is RSU Ibnu Sina Makassar

Populations and Samples

The population in this study were all employees of Ibnu Sina Hospital. The number of samples in this study was 78 respondents .

Data Collection Methods

Data collection was carried out using a questionnaire created by researchers referring to the conceptual framework and variables to be studied for respondents. Researchers will provide a questionnaire in the form of a Google Form questionnaire to be filled out by Ibnu Sina Hospital employees, consisting of 4 questionnaire items, namely communication, leadership, motivation and team performance.

Data Analysis Methods

In this research, data analysis was carried out after the data from the questionnaire was collected and then re-checked to determine the completeness of the content. After the complete data was collected and tabulated based on the sub-variables studied, then calculations were carried out using the SPSS program using path analysis. Path analysis aims to determine the direct or indirect influence of exogenous (independent) variables on endogenous (dependent) variables with significance (Sigma F) < 0.05 and significance (Sigma T) < 0.05 .

RESULT

General Characteristics of Respondents

Based on table 2, based on the results of research conducted at Ibnu Sina Hospital, it was found that the age characteristics of the majority of respondents were between 21 and 40 years old, which accounted for 69 people or 88.5% of the total respondents. Meanwhile, only 9 people aged 41 to 60 years or 11.5%.

Table 2

Characteristics		n	%
Age	21-40 years old	69	88.5
	41-60 years old	9	11.5
Gender	Man	13	16.7
	Woman	65	83.3
length of working	1-5 years	12	15.4
	> 5 years	66	84.6
Education	SMA/SPK	2	2.6
	DIII	27	34.6
	S1	23	29.5
	S2	4	5.1
	S3	1	1.3
	Profession	21	26.9

Based on gender, the majority of respondents were women, reaching 65 people or 83.3%, while only 13 men or 16.7%.

In terms of length of work characteristics, the majority of respondents have worked for more than 5 years, with 66 people or 84.6%, while only 12 people or 15.4% have worked between 1 and 5 years.

Based on education level, the majority of respondents had a DIII education level, with 27 people or 34.6%, followed by S1 with 23 people or 29.5%. Higher levels of education such as Masters and Doctoral degrees had fewer respondents, respectively 4 people or 5.1% and 1 person or 1.3%. There were also 21 respondents or 26.9% who had certain professions

Bivariate Analysis

The results of the bivariate analysis will see the relationship between the independent variables one by one and the dependent variable. So in this research we can see the relationship between the variables remuneration, satisfaction, motivation and performance.

Based on table 3 , it is found that **Communication**: Of the 77 respondents who thought communication was good, 74 people or 96.1% had high performance. Although this percentage shows a positive trend, the p value of 0.051 indicates that there is no relationship between good communication and high performance with grades ($p < 0.05$). This means that the absence of good communication relationships significantly affects performance.

Table 3

Variables/Categories			Team performance		Amount	p value
			Tall	Low		
Communication	Good	n	74	3	77	0.051
		%	96.1%	3.9%	100.0%	
	Not good	n	0	1	1	
		%	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
Motivation	Tall	n	72	2	74	0.012
		%	97.3%	2.7%	100.0%	
	Low	n	2	2	4	
		%	50.0%	50.0%	100.0%	
Leadership	Tall	n	74	0	74	0,000
		%	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%	
	Low	n	0	4	4	
		%	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
Amount		n	74	4	78	
		%	94.9%	5.1%	100.0%	

Motivation: Of the 74 respondents who had high motivation, 72 people or 97.3% had high performance. The low p value, namely 0.012, indicates that the relationship between high motivation and high performance has statistical significance of ($p < 0.05$). This shows that high motivation is significantly related to high team performance at Ibnu Sina Hospital.

Leadership: All respondents (100.0%) who consider a high level of leadership also have high performance. The very low p value, namely 0.000, indicates that the relationship between high levels of leadership and high performance is highly statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This confirms that good leadership significantly contributes to high team performance at Ibnu Sina Hospital).

Multivariate Analysis

Based on the results of the analysis in table 4, it is found that **Leadership --> Communication**: There is a significant positive influence of leadership on communication. The estimated coefficient of 0.791 indicates that every one unit increase in the leadership variable will be followed by an increase of 0.791 units in the communication variable. The p value ($0.000 < 0.05$) concluded that there was a significant influence of the leadership variable on communication at Ibnu Sina Hospital.

Table 4

Direct Effect of Variables			Estimate Standardized	S.E	CR	p value	Label
Leadership	-->	Communication	0.791	0.044	11,353	0,000	Direct
Communication	-->	Motivation	0.314	0.077	2,889	0.004	Direct
Leadership	-->	Motivation	0.540	0.049	4,969	0,000	Direct
Motivation	-->	Performance	0.228	0.268	3,115	0.002	Direct
Communication	-->	Performance	0.169	0.190	2,291	0.022	Direct
Leadership	-->	Performance	0.592	0.132	7,367	0,000	Direct

Communication --> Motivation: There is a significant positive influence of the communication variable on motivation. This means that every one unit increase in the communication variable will be followed by an increase of 0.314 units in the motivation variable. The p value ($0.004 < 0.05$) can be concluded that there is a significant positive influence of the communication variable on motivation at Ibnu Sina Hospital.

Leadership --> Motivation: There is a significant positive influence of leadership on motivation. The estimated coefficient of 0.540 indicates that every one unit increase in the leadership variable will be followed by an increase of 0.540 units in the motivation variable. The very low p value (0.000) confirms the statistical significance of this relationship.

Motivation --> Performance: There is a significant positive influence of motivation on performance. Every one unit increase in the motivation variable will be followed by an increase of 0.228 units in the performance variable. The low p value (0.002) indicates the statistical significance of this relationship.

Communication --> Performance: There is a significant positive influence of communication on performance. This means that every one unit increase in the communication variable will be followed by an increase of 0.169 units in the performance variable. The low p value (0.022) indicates the statistical significance of this relationship.

Leadership --> Performance: There is a significant positive influence of leadership on performance. Every one unit increase in the leadership variable will be followed by an increase of 0.592 units in the performance variable. The very low p value (0.000) confirms the statistical significance of this relationship. Apart from using more than one independent variable, this research also uses intervening variables. Intervening variables are mediating variables whose function is to mediate the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. To test intervening variables, the following path analysis method is used:

Figure 2: Path Analysis of Research Variables

Based on the picture above, it shows the influence of the independent variables and intervening variables on the dependent variable, both directly, indirectly and in total.

Apart from that, there is also an indirect influence from leadership and communication variables on performance through motivation variables. This shows the complexity of the relationships between variables and the importance of paying attention to these factors simultaneously in improving organizational performance .

Communication --> Motivation --> Performance (Indirect) : The estimated value of 0.072 indicates that there is an indirect relationship between the communication variable and performance through the motivation variable. This means that every one unit increase in the communication variable indirectly contributes to an increase of 0.072 units in performance through an increase in the motivation variable.

Leadership --> Motivation --> Performance (Indirect) : The estimated value of 0.123 indicates that there is an indirect relationship between the leadership variable and performance through the motivation variable. This means, every one unit increase in the leadership variable will indirectly contribute to an increase of 0.123 units in performance through an increase in the motivation variable

DISCUSSION

The Influence of *Leadership* on Communication in Implementing Patient Safety Culture at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar

Based on the results of research conducted at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar, it was found that leadership has a positive and significant influence on communication in implementing patient safety culture. The results of the analysis show that the estimated coefficient is 0.791, which indicates that every one unit increase in the leadership variable will be followed by an increase of 0.791 units in the communication variable. Furthermore, the p value obtained is 0.000, which is smaller than the specified significance level (0.05), so it can be concluded that there is a significant influence of the leadership variable on communication at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar.

In a broader context, this research contributes to the understanding of the factors that influence patient safety culture in hospitals, and emphasizes the importance of paying attention to leadership and communication dimensions in efforts to improve the quality of health services and overall patient safety.

These results are in line with research by Schultz, (2021) which states that there is a positive relationship between self-leadership and work engagement and the future of HRM. Furthermore, research by Rembet et al., (2023) stated that there was a significant influence between Self-leadership training and *Clinical Leadership Competency*. The results of this research are supported by the findings of Yandri Dems de Haan and his colleagues (2022), which show that leadership style also has an impact on employee performance and their satisfaction.

The Direct Influence of Communication on Motivation in Implementing Patient Safety Culture at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar

Based on the results of research conducted at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar, it was found that there was a significant positive influence of communication variables on motivation in implementing patient safety culture. The analysis shows that every one unit increase in the communication variable will be followed by an increase of 0.314

units in the motivation variable. In addition, the p value obtained was 0.004, smaller than the specified significance level (0.05), indicating a significant positive influence of the communication variable on motivation at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar

So it can be concluded that these findings confirm that good communication can be the key to motivating hospital staff to implement an effective patient safety culture. Therefore, efforts to improve communication between team members and leaders can be an important strategy in increasing awareness and commitment to patient safety at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar.

Communication is the process of sending or receiving messages from one individual to another individual, either directly or indirectly, through various means such as oral, written, or nonverbal language. This finding is in line with the results of Desy Ernika's (2016) research on the impact of organizational communication and motivation on employee performance at PT. Inti Tractors Samarinda. Data analysis shows that the t-count value is 12,214, while the t-table value is 3,170

The Influence of *Leadership* on Motivation in Implementing Patient Safety Culture at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar

Based on the research results, there is a direct influence of variables. Based on the results of research conducted at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar, it was found that there was a significant positive influence of leadership on motivation in implementing patient safety culture. Data analysis shows that the estimated coefficient is 0.540, which indicates that every one unit increase in the leadership variable will be followed by an increase of 0.540 units in the motivation variable. Furthermore, the very low p value, namely 0.000, confirms the statistical significance of this relationship, indicating that the influence of leadership on motivation is significantly significant at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar.

This finding is in line with the results of research by Silaban and colleagues (2021), which confirms that leadership has a significant impact on motivation. Other research conducted by Agustin and his team (2019) also supports this finding by showing that leadership has a significant influence on motivation.

The Influence of *Motivation* on Team Performance in implementing Patient Safety Culture at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar

The results of analysis in research conducted at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar show that there is a significant positive influence of motivation on performance in implementing patient safety culture. It was found that every one unit increase in the motivation variable will be followed by an increase of 0.228 units in the performance variable. In addition, the low p value, namely 0.002, shows the statistical significance of this relationship, indicating that the influence of motivation on performance is statistically significant at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar.

These findings confirm that motivation has an important role in improving performance in implementing patient safety culture in hospitals. Therefore, hospital management needs to pay attention to efforts to increase staff motivation as part of an overall strategy to improve patient safety and the quality of health services at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar.

Organizations need to increase employee motivation to achieve maximum goals. This finding is in line with research conducted by Sukatendel and his colleagues (2021), which shows that partial motivation has a significant influence on employee performance. The results of other research published in an international journal by Saari (2021) also confirm that motivation has an impact on employee performance.

The Direct Influence of Communication on Performance in Implementing Patient Safety Culture at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar

Based on the results of the analysis carried out at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar, it was found that there was a significant positive influence from communication on performance in implementing patient safety culture. This means that every one unit increase in the communication variable will be followed by an increase of 0.169 units in the performance variable. With a p value of 0.022, which is lower than the specified significance level (0.05), indicating the statistical significance of this relationship at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar.

This research is supported by research conducted by Wadijaya (2018) and Yulianti (2017). They found that the way we communicate has a big impact on how well we perform at work. So, if we can communicate well, it is likely that our performance will also improve. This research wants to better understand why this happens and how we can use communication to work better.

The Influence of Leadership on Team Performance in Implementing Patient Safety Culture at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar

From the results of the analysis carried out at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar, it was found that there was a significant positive influence of leadership on performance in implementing patient safety culture. Every one unit increase in the leadership variable will be followed by an increase of 0.592 units in the performance variable. With a very low p value of 0.000, the statistical significance of this relationship is confirmed.

These findings confirm that effective leadership has a significant impact on performance in implementing patient safety culture in hospitals. Therefore, developing quality leadership can be an important strategy in efforts to improve patient safety and the quality of health services at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar.

This research is in line with the results of research conducted by Aidin (2021) and Koleangan (2017), which shows that the way a leader leads has a positive influence on employee performance. Leaders must be able to give clear instructions to each team member, monitor their work, and motivate them to carry out tasks according to the plans that have been made. Thus, this research confirms that the role of a leader is very important in guiding and encouraging employees to achieve the best performance

The Indirect Influence of Communication on Team Performance through Motivation in Implementing Patient Safety Culture at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar

The results of the analysis show that there is an indirect relationship between communication variables and performance through motivation variables in implementing patient safety culture at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar. The estimated value of 0.072 indicates that every one unit increase in the communication variable indirectly contributes to an increase of 0.072 units in performance through an increase

in the motivation variable. In conclusion, these findings emphasize the importance of understanding the role of communication and motivation in improving performance in the implementation of patient safety culture. By strengthening these two factors, hospitals can create a work environment that supports and motivates staff to be actively involved in patient safety practices, which in turn will improve the overall safety and quality of health services at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar.

Based on previous research conducted by Eva Silvani Lawasi (2017), it was found that the variables of communication, motivation and teamwork had a positive and significant influence on improving employee performance. These results are in line with current research. This means that both previous research and current research show the similarity that communication, motivation and teamwork have a positive and significant impact on increasing the performance of team members. This confirms the importance of these factors in achieving better performance in the work environment.

The Indirect Influence of Leadership on Team Performance through Motivation in Implementing Patient Safety Culture at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar

Based on the results of research conducted at Ibnu Sina Hospital Makassar, it was found that there was an indirect influence between leadership variables and performance through motivation variables in implementing patient safety culture. The estimated value of 0.123 indicates that every one unit increase in the leadership variable will indirectly contribute to an increase of 0.123 units in performance through an increase in the motivation variable.

The relationship between leadership and improved performance has been proven in a variety of types of organizations and cultures. A person's response to organizational change, individual perception, and receptivity to innovation are all influenced by the leadership style in the organization. The concept of leadership continues to develop along with changes in knowledge, culture and environment. Research by Asbari et al. (2021) also shows that Self-Leadership has a big impact on work innovation and can increase nurses' knowledge. The results of this study show a significant relationship between knowledge and nurses' innovative work attitudes.

According to research conducted by Rembet et al. (2023), the Ordinal Logistic Regression Test shows that Self-Leadership Training has a significant influence on Clinical Leadership Competency, with Nagelkerke Pseudo R-Square reaching 0.143. This means that Self-Leadership training is able to influence clinical leadership abilities by 14.3%, while the remaining 85.7% is influenced by other factors outside the scope of this research.

CONCLUSION

Based on research results, leadership has a significant influence on communication, motivation and performance. Communication has a significant influence on motivation and performance. Motivation has a significant influence on performance. There is an indirect influence between communication and performance through motivation. There is an indirect influence between leadership and performance through motivation. Good communication and effective leadership can influence performance indirectly by increasing the motivation of team members at RSU Ibnu Sina Makassar.

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